

Explainable Reinforcement Learning for Trajectory Design in UAV-assisted Wireless Networks

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Abstract—Unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs) used as aerial base stations show significant promise for future wireless communication systems. This paper explores using a UAV as an autonomous agent, navigating over multiple hotspots to serve ground users (GUs) and maximize data transmission rates through strategic trajectory design. Existing interpretability methods often prove insufficient in providing comprehensive insights and generating logical, sequential decisions. In this paper, we propose an explainable reinforcement learning framework designed to produce interpretable and verifiable agent policies. Our method starts with an expert optimizer to solve training examples, enabling the learning agent (UAV) to analyse the solutions. Furthermore, we employ inverse reinforcement learning for data-driven reward function estimation. Additionally, we use a probabilistic Q-table function to understand and explain the actions executed by the expert across diverse environmental contexts, allowing the learning agent to produce interpretable policies that meet reasonable performance goals and easily transferred to unseen environments. Preliminary results indicate that the proposed approach is promising in achieving explainability in RL agents.

Index Terms—UAV, RL, XRL, IRL, TSP.

I. INTRODUCTION

Unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs), acting as flying base stations, show great promise in significantly improving the efficiency of wireless systems with exceptionally high and dynamic traffic demands [1], [2]. With their exceptional mobility, flexible deployment, minimal installation restrictions, and low construction costs, UAV-assisted communications are becoming increasingly crucial in modern wireless networks [3]. By adjusting their positions, UAVs can efficiently establish direct links with ground users, leading to improved communication. Moreover, the controllable manoeuvrability of UAVs enables flexible trajectory planning, providing additional freedom to enhance system capacity [4].

UAV trajectory planning has been extensively studied in the literature in order to optimize various communication utilities, such as throughput, communication coverage, completion time, and energy efficiency [5], [6]. Traditional methods for trajectory design have approached the problem by treating it as a combinatorial optimization problem, similar to the travelling salesman problem (TSP) [7]. The TSP entails finding the shortest path that visits all locations (i.e., hotspots) in a network before eventually returning to the starting point, making it an NP-hard problem in combinatorial optimization. To tackle this NP-hard problem, the studies in [8]–[10] strategically utilized the TSP solution as a feasible initialized trajectory in their proposed iterative algorithms and achieved significant results.

Conventional trajectory design methods mainly focus on optimizing deterministic systems where all system information is known [11]. They are suitable for offline planning, but traditional optimization methods may not be practical for online planning and autonomous decision-making in uncertain real-world conditions. Reinforcement learning (RL) provides a practical solution to this challenge by allowing smart UAVs to engage with the environment and adjust their strategies to effectively achieve predefined system objectives [12], [13].

The work in [14] utilized RL to deploy UAVs for providing on-demand wireless service to ground users (GUs). Similarly, a multi-agent Q-learning-based algorithm was proposed for flexible UAV trajectory design based on predictions of user mobility in [15]. In another work [16], deep RL methods were used to guide energy-limited UAVs in providing fair coverage for GUs under energy constraints and environmental dynamics. Additionally, an RL approach in [17] was developed to enable a UAV to serve as a data-collection relay, maximizing information freshness. However, the internal dynamics of the RL solutions in [14]–[17]—such as hyperparameters, exploration strategies, and loss functions—rely on manually adjusted parameters, making them vulnerable to environmental changes and limiting their adaptability to new situations.

Designing a generalized reward function in RL is quite challenging, particularly in large and complex environments where capturing dynamic stability is difficult [18]. However, imitation learning (IL) provides a way for UAVs to learn strategies directly from expert demonstrations, bypassing the need for complex reward function design [19]–[22]. Behaviour cloning (BC), a deep IL technique [23]–[26], trains models by mimicking expert demonstrations without requiring a reward function. However, it faces difficulties in matching state-action distributions and generalizing beyond demonstrated scenarios [27], [28]. To alleviate the drawback of BC, the DAGger algorithm [29]–[31] employs online learning to correct abnormalities in unseen situations [32]. However, online interactions can be costly or risky in practical scenarios, making DAGger challenging to implement without continuous supervision [33]. On the other hand, inverse reinforcement learning (IRL) infers reward functions from expert behavior, overcoming the RL's reward design challenges. Moreover, it offers insights into expert actions, adapting to new environments, and improving through real interaction [34]–[36].

This study presents an explainable reinforcement learning (XRL) methodology aiming to develop lucid and corroborated

tive agent policies that integrate imitation learning, inverse reinforcement learning, and reinforcement learning. Imitation learning is employed to scrutinize the demonstrations provided by the expert optimizer, enabling an understanding of the strategy it employed to solve the training examples and enabling the learning agent (UAV) to analyze the solutions. Additionally, inverse reinforcement learning is leveraged for data-driven reward function estimation by deducing the rewards associated with each example in a data-driven fashion. A probabilistic Q-table is utilized to comprehend and elucidate the actions executed by the expert across varied environmental contexts, thereby enabling the learning agent to encode not only the correlation between state actions and corresponding reward values but also a spectrum of potential solutions contingent upon the agent's encountered diversity. This facilitates the production of lucid policies by the learning agent that align with rational performance objectives and demonstrate robustness while being readily transferable to unobserved environments.

II. SYSTEM MODEL AND PROBLEM FORMULATION

Consider a UAV-assisted communication system in the \mathcal{R} region, $\mathcal{R} \subset \mathbb{R}^3$. The UAV-BS provides wireless communication services to N ground users (GUs) randomly distributed on the ground. We assume GUs to be classified into M distinct groups, each referred to as hotspot. Each hotspot m is identified by its center $c_m = [x_m, y_m]$, and the average data rate R_m that depends on the number of active users within hotspot m . The UAV-BS aims to depart from its initial location, travel towards the hotspots with high data service demands, and return within a flight time of T to recharge its battery. Thus, the initial and final positions of UAV are predefined as $p_0 = p_f = [x_0, y_0, z_0]$, respectively. For a certain hotspot distribution, the set of all possible trajectories UAV might follow is denoted by ξ . The sequence recording the UAV's tours among the hotspots within flight time of T is captured by $\mathbf{q}_u = [l_1, l_2, \dots, l_{M'}]$, where $l_m \in M$ denotes the m -th hotspot served by the UAV, and M' is the total number of hotspots served along the mission and $\mathbf{q}_u \in \xi$. The travel distance for the UAV to fly from hotspot i to hotspot j is given by: $c_{ij} = \sqrt{(x_i - x_j)^2 + (y_i - y_j)^2}$, where $i \in \mathbf{q}_u$ and $j \in \mathbf{q}_u$. UAV flight duration (T) is divided into K equal time slots, where the size of a single time slot is $t = (\frac{T}{K})$. Each time slot t assumes constant UAV position, uplink data requests, and channel conditions due to its short period. Additionally, UAV allocates one uplink resource block (RB) per GU in a specific hotspot and the GUs use these RBs to transmit their data using OFDMA technique. We adopted the air-to-ground signal propagation model, incorporating a probabilistic path loss model that accounts for both line-of-sight (LoS) and Non-line-of sight (NLoS) conditions [2]. Consequently, the channel gain between GU n and UAV (u) can be manifested as:

$$h_{n,u}(t) = \frac{1}{\mathbb{W}_0 d_{n,u}^\alpha(t)} [\text{Pr}_{\text{LoS}} \delta_{\text{LoS}} + \text{Pr}_{\text{NLoS}} \delta_{\text{NLoS}}]^{-1}, \quad (1)$$

where $\mathbb{W}_0 = (\frac{4\pi f_c}{c})^2$, f_c represents the carrier frequency, c is the speed of light, α indicates the path loss exponent. The distance between GU n and the UAV (u) at time slot t is demonstrated by $d_{u_m,v}(t) = \sqrt{(x_n(t) - x_u(t))^2 + (y_n(t) - y_u(t))^2 + z_u^2(t)}$. Pr_{LoS} and Pr_{NLoS} reflects the probabilities of LoS and NLoS, respectively. δ_{LoS} and δ_{NLoS} are additional attenuation factors for LoS and NLoS links compared to free-space propagation. The average achievable data rate of the set of users N_m in hotspot m is described as:

$$R_{N_m} = \sum_{u_m=1}^{N_m} R_{u_m} = \sum_{u_m=1}^{N_m} B_{u_m} \log_2 \left(1 + \frac{\rho_{u_m} h_{u_m,u}(t)}{\vartheta^2} \right), \quad (2)$$

where B_{u_m} is the bandwidth of the RB assigned to GU (u_m), ρ_{u_m} is the transmit power of GU (u_m), and $\vartheta^2 = B_{u_m} N_0$ represents the power spectral density of the additive white Gaussian noise (AWGN).

Finding the best trajectory to maximize the total sum-rate and minimize travel distance can be viewed as a TSP with profit problem. Thus, the objective function of the problem can be expressed as:

$$\min_{\mathbf{q}_u \in \xi} \quad \alpha \sum_{(i,j) \in \mathbf{q}_u} a_{ij} c_{ij} - \beta \sum_{j \in \mathbf{q}_u} b_j R_j, \quad (3a)$$

$$\text{s.t.} \quad a_{ij} \in \{0, 1\}, \quad (i, j) \in \mathbf{q}_u, \quad (3b)$$

$$b_j \in \{0, 1\}, \quad j \in \mathbf{q}_u, \quad (3c)$$

$$\alpha + \beta = 1. \quad (3d)$$

In (3a), binary variables a_{ij} is associated with the transition from hotspot i to hotspot j and is set to 1 only if (i, j) is used in the solution. In (3b), binary variables b_{ij} is associated with hotspot j and is set to 1 only if j is visited.

III. PROPOSED METHOD

The proposed methodology integrates imitation learning (IL) and inverse reinforcement learning (IRL) to develop an explainable reinforcement learning (RL) method. This is achieved by analyzing the demonstrations provided by an expert and estimating the corresponding rewards encoded in the probabilistic Q-table. The objective is to explain how the rewards could change based on the actions taken in specific states and how the learning agent can apply this knowledge to explain solving new examples.

A. Expert demonstrations

Let $\mathcal{D} = \{D_1, D_2, \dots, D_E\}$ represent a set of training examples. Each example includes the number of hotspots and their locations, the number of users within each hotspot, and the users' access requests and locations. The expert employs an optimizer to find a solution for those examples by solving (3a) using the 2-OPT method [37], providing a set of demonstrations representing the optimal trajectories encoded in $\mathcal{Q} = \{\mathbf{q}_{u,1}, \mathbf{q}_{u,2}, \dots, \mathbf{q}_{u,E}\}$, where $\mathbf{q}_{u,e} = \{l_{1,e}, l_{2,e}, \dots, l_{M',e}\}$ is the e -th solution (optimal trajectory) of the e -th example.

B. Reward estimation

The expert's set of demonstrations is analyzed to estimate the reward for each (state, action) pair encoded in the solution in a data-driven fashion. Let's consider a specific example that can be viewed as a set of states and actions. The states are represented by the hotspot index $l_{1,e}$, and the action involves transitioning from one hotspot to another while respecting the correct order. Therefore, we have $\mathbf{q}_{u,e} = \{(s_1 = l_{1,e}, a_1 = l_{1,e} \rightarrow l_{2,e}), (s_2 = l_{2,e}, a_2 = l_{2,e} \rightarrow l_{3,e}), \dots, (s_{M'-1} = l_{M'-1,e}, a_{M'-1} = l_{M'-1,e} \rightarrow l_{M',e})\}$. Subsequently, a probabilistic q-table is developed to encode the states and actions observed in each demonstration. The q-table is defined as follows:

$$Q_e = \begin{bmatrix} \Pr(s_1 = l_{1,e} | s_1 = l_{1,e}) & \dots & \Pr(s_1 = l_{1,e} | s_{M'} = l_{M',e}) \\ \Pr(s_2 = l_{2,e} | s_1 = l_{1,e}) & \dots & \Pr(s_2 = l_{2,e} | s_{M'} = l_{M',e}) \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots \\ \Pr(s_{M'} = l_{M',e} | s_1 = l_{1,e}) & \dots & \Pr(s_{M'} = l_{M',e} | s_{M'} = l_{M',e}) \end{bmatrix}, \quad (4)$$

where $\Pr(s_i = l_{i,e} | s_j = l_{j,e}) = 1$ if $(i, i) \in \mathbf{q}_{u,e}$, otherwise zero.

Consequently, we create an incremental probabilistic Q-table encoding the states and the actions performed over all the E demonstrations. This is achieved by calculating the average of all the Q_e tables related to each example. The global Q-table is defined as:

$$Q = \begin{bmatrix} \Pr(s_1 | s_1) & \Pr(s_1 | s_2) & \dots & \Pr(s_1 | s_F) \\ \Pr(s_2 | s_1) & \Pr(s_2 | s_2) & \dots & \Pr(s_2 | s_F) \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots \\ \Pr(s_F | s_1) & \Pr(s_F | s_2) & \dots & \Pr(s_F | s_F) \end{bmatrix}, \quad (5)$$

where $\Pr(s_f | s_f) = 0$, $0 \leq \Pr(s_f | s_{f'}) \leq 1$ and $\sum_{f'=1}^F \Pr(s_f | s_{f'}) = 1, \forall f$.

C. Online Mapping for explanation of trajectory generation

The probabilistic Q-table's peculiarity allows us to explain the expert's action preferences, unlike the traditional Q-table with real values that cannot provide such insights. The problem of trajectory planning in RL can be conceptualized as a Markov decision process. In our system model, an UAV observes the environmental state at time t , executes an action based on a predefined policy, and subsequently receives the ensuing reward from the environment and an updated state. The selection of actions is contingent upon the Q-table, which is constructed during the training phase. In the process of online action selection, conventional RL methods exclusively exploit actions listed in the Q-table, which may lead to challenges when encountering novel states and exploring new actions. To address this issue, we advance the proposal of generating alternative solutions representative of various courses of action using the probabilistic Q-table. These solutions are subsequently compared with the current context confronting the agent to explain how the agent could solve a new situation by projecting it onto a task it knows how to solve, thus overcoming the limitations arising from solely relying actions stored in the Q-table and implicitly expanding it. The UAV agent uses the table defined in equation (5) to

plan its trajectory online based on the situation it is facing, which is determined by the available hotspots represented by the set $Z = [l_1^\dagger, l_2^\dagger, \dots, l_{M'}^\dagger]$. The UAV starts by generating a set of imagined trajectories (\mathcal{Q}^*), i.e., the sequence of hotspots it intends to visit from the table according to: $\mathcal{Q}^* = [q_1^*, q_2^*, \dots, q_L^*]$. Before deciding on the trajectory to follow, the UAV first identifies its intended sequence of hotspots to visit, denoted as $\mathbf{q}_l^* = [l_1^*, l_2^*, \dots, l_{M'}^*]$. It then assesses various alternative trajectories by comparing the distances between the hotspots in these trajectories and the current situation it faces. For each possible generated trajectory in \mathcal{Q}^* , a graph matching is performed and encoded in the following matching matrix:

$$\mathbb{M}_l^* = \begin{bmatrix} d(l_1^\dagger | l_1^*) & d(l_1^\dagger | l_2^*) & \dots & d(l_1^\dagger | l_{M'}^*) \\ d(l_2^\dagger | l_1^*) & d(l_2^\dagger | l_2^*) & \dots & d(l_2^\dagger | l_{M'}^*) \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots \\ d(l_{M'}^\dagger | l_1^*) & d(l_{M'}^\dagger | l_2^*) & \dots & d(l_{M'}^\dagger | l_{M'}^*) \end{bmatrix}, \quad (6)$$

where $d(l_i^\dagger | l_j^*) = \sqrt{(x_{l_i^\dagger} - x_{l_j^*})^2 + (y_{l_i^\dagger} - y_{l_j^*})^2}$. Consequently, the agent chooses the matrix with the highest matching probability and then selects the corresponding imagined trajectory from \mathcal{Q}^* to use as a reference for solving the new situation.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

In this section, we present preliminary results to evaluate the proposed methodology for achieving explainable reinforcement learning by integrating Imitation Learning (IL) and Inverse Reinforcement Learning (IRL). Our simulations were conducted in a scenario where a single UAV serves multiple users located in various hotspots across a 1000×1000 square meter geographic area. The simulation parameters are detailed as follows [38]: $P_u = 1W$, $B_{RB} = 180KHz$, $\mu_{LoS} = 3$, $\mu_{NLoS} = 23$, $\sigma^2 = -104dBm$, $\alpha = 0.9$, $\beta = 0.1$. During the training phase, 25 hotspots were randomly placed across the designated area. The Poisson distribution was employed to generate user presence and requests within each hotspot. Our training set comprised $M = 1000$ examples of diverse hotspot distributions, with each example encompassing five randomly selected hotspots from the available ones. The expert optimizer with 2-OPT was utilized to solve 1000 examples, resulting in 1000 trajectories from which we obtained the Q-table. For testing, a total of 50 hotspots were made available. In each testing example, a specific number of hotspots were randomly selected to be addressed by the UAV via pure online means, utilizing the Q-table to plan its actions and address the testing examples. Furthermore, we compared the performance of the proposed XRL method against traditional Q-learning (Random-RL), employing the same Q-table used by XRL to ensure equitable comparison.

In Fig. 1, we conducted a comparative analysis of the preliminary performance of the proposed XRL in relation to both random-RL and an expert optimizer utilizing the 2-OPT method. The comparison was based on the average cost with profit, representing the objective function defined in (3a), and completion time during the resolution of testing examples.

Fig. 1. Comparing expert optimizer (2-OPT), XRL, and random-RL performance by varying the number of hotspots.

Fig. 2. Similarity rate by comparing the solutions produced by XRL, random-RL compared to those produced by the expert optimizer (2-OPT).

Our primary objective is to furnish the UAV agent with the capability to effectively address new examples after training on existing ones and articulate the solution in a manner that aligns with the optimizer’s performance, thereby enabling the acquisition of the essential skills required to address diverse scenarios. The XRL model outperforms random-RL by selecting a solution from a pool of alternative solutions that mimic the strategy used by the optimizer. In contrast, random-RL makes selections randomly without providing clear explanations or justifications for its choices. The figure demonstrates how the proposed XRL can closely approach the optimizer in terms of cost with profit and completion time with a low number of hotspots. However, as the number of hotspots increases, the testing examples become more complicated, and the gap between the proposed XRL and the optimizer also increases. This occurs because the matching between imagined solutions and the current situation becomes more complex, requiring advanced steps to efficiently perform such mapping, which will be addressed in future work.

In Fig. 2, the similarity rates between the solutions provided by the proposed XRL and the random-RL are demonstrated compared to the solutions provided by the expert. The results indicate that the proposed XRL produces solutions that are more similar to those offered by the optimizer, as opposed to those generated by the random-RL. Even though the similarity rate of the proposed XRL decreases as the number of hotspots decreases, it still holds promise as it enables the agent to suggest alternative feasible solutions by sacrificing certain factors, thereby showcasing creativity.

Fig. 3. Comparing expert optimizer (2-OPT), XRL, and random-RL in trajectory design to solve several testing examples.

In Fig. 3, various testing scenarios are displayed with different numbers of hotspots, accompanied by the trajectories generated by the proposed XRL, random-RL, and the optimizer (2-OPT). The XRL method produces solutions resembling those of the optimizer when dealing with a small number of hotspots, confirming the results displayed in Figure 1. This suggests that XRL has effectively grasped the optimizer’s strategy and acquired the necessary skills to handle new situations never seen before. Ultimately, this leads to the generation of superior solutions compared to random-RL. Nevertheless, the trajectories developed by the XRL deteriorate as the number of hotspots increases, but they still represent feasible trajectories that can be utilized in emergency and extraordinary circumstances.

V. CONCLUSION

This paper investigates using a UAV as an autonomous agent to navigate multiple hotspots, serve ground users, reduce completion time, and maximize data transmission rates. It suggests a method of explainable reinforcement learning to create understandable and verifiable agent policies. The method utilizes an expert optimizer, inverse reinforcement learning, and probabilistic Q-tables to comprehend and clarify expert actions in various environmental contexts. It also incorporates online graph matching to learn how to apply previous solutions in new situations. Initial results are promising in achieving explainability in RL agents. Future work aims to enhance the graph matching and will involve reward decomposition to achieve high levels of explainability and enhance performance as the number of hotspots increases.

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